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**A STUDY ON MOTIVATION LEVEL OF MANAGERS AND ITS IMPACT ON
PERFORMANCE IN INSURANCE INDUSTRY AT PUNE CITY**

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Abstract:

In organizations, it is important to determine both current and future organizational requirements for both core employees and the contingent workforce in terms of their skills/technical abilities, competencies, flexibility etc. The analysis requires consideration of the internal and external factors that can have an effect on the resourcing, development, motivation and retention of employees and other workers.

External factors are those largely out-with the control of the organization. These include issues such as economic climate and current and future labor market trends (e.g., skills, education level, government investment into industries etc.). On the other hand, internal influences are broadly controlled by the organization to predict, determine, and monitor—for example—the organizational culture, underpinned by management style, environmental climate, and the approach to ethical and corporate social responsibilities.

I Introduction:

Motivating employees can be a challenging task when learning how to supervise people. In order to drive your employees to be perform at their best it helps to understand what motivates people. The key factors that motivate people. Understanding these factors can help in finding the right solutions in motivating employees.

One of the keys to being a successful manager is the ability to motivate employees to perform at their best. When employees aren't interested in their work or they're bored, employee morale is low and productivity drops. Generally, employees are willing and able to work if they feel their job is important and they are appreciated. When motivating employees there are two main types of rewards, intrinsic reward and extrinsic reward.

People are motivated in different ways, one of which is by intrinsic reward. Intrinsic rewards or intrinsic motivation primarily deals with the feelings an employee has when they have done a good job.

They do it because they enjoy it. This can be seen more in hobbies or in the feeling of obligation to do well at ones job. The second type of reward is extrinsic. Extrinsic rewards or extrinsic motivation refers to a tangible or intangible reward given to you by someone else. Praise, pay increases, bonuses, and promotions are a few examples of extrinsic rewards. The traditional method of motivating employees has been used extrinsic motivation. In order to better understand how to motivate employees you must first understand how motivation works. According to Abraham Maslow, people are motivated by unmet needs. Maslow's hierarchy of needs:

1. Psychological needs – these are your basic survival needs, like food, water, and shelter.
2. Safety needs – employees want to feel secure at work.
3. Social needs – the need to feel accepted and part of the group.
4. Esteem needs – the need for acknowledgement and recognition from others.
5. Self-actualization needs – the need to develop to your fullest potential.

In theory, when one of these needs is met a person will start to satisfy the next need. As a manager it is important to understand the types of needs you are dealing with.

II Review of Literature:

The Michigan model is based on the paradigms developed by Chandler (1962) and Galbraith and Nathanson (1978). It is argued that an organization's structure is an outcome of its strategy (Chandler, 1962). This argument was extended by linking different personnel functions

such as career paths, rewards, and leadership styles to the organization's mission (Galbraith and Nathanson, 1978). The matching model has been criticized as being too prescriptive by nature mainly due to the fact that its assumptions are too unitarist (Boxall, 1992).

It emphasizes a 'tight fit' between organizational strategy and HR strategies and, while doing so, completely ignores the interest of employees and hence considers HR as a totally passive, reactive, and implementation function. The model's emphasis on tight fit makes the organization inflexible and incapable of adapting to the required changes and hence is a 'misfit' in today's dynamic business environment. The very idea of the model to consider and use human resources like any other resources in an organization seems unpragmatic as it misses the human aspect. Despite many criticisms, the matching model provides a good framework to theory development in the field of HRM. It also provides a promising schema to look at the HR practices in universal and generic term. It, however, ignores the cultural processes. The matching model and the Harvard analytical framework represent two very different emphases

The former is closer to strategic management literature while the latter to human relations tradition. Some aspects of the basic philosophy of 'soft HRM' can be traced back to the writings of McGregor (1960) who, as mentioned by Truss (1999), even used the terminology 'hard' and 'soft' to characterize the forms of management control. McGregor's Theory X describes the 'control' model of management (Walton, 1985) while Theory Y emphasizes the importance of integrating the needs of the organization and those of the individual

The principle of mutual trust again being expressed by Walton (1985) The soft model of HRM traces its roots to the Human Relations School. It involves "treating employees as valued assets, a source of competitive advantage through their commitment, adaptability, and high quality of skills, performance etc." (Storey, 1992)

HRM as a concept emerged in the mid-1980s with the efforts of the writers of management of that decade including Pascale and Athos (1981) and Peters and Waterman (1982) who listed the attributes which they claimed as characterizing successful companies. The 'school of excellence' writers may have exerted some influence on management thinking about the need

for strong culture and commitment (two features of HRM) but, they were 'right enough to be dangerously wrong' (Guest, 1993).

It has, however, been observed that "even if the rhetoric of HRM is soft, the reality is often hard with the interests of the organization prevailing over those of the individual" (Truss, 1999). Gratton *et al.* (1999) identified a combination of soft and hard HRM approaches in the eight organizations studied. The Western countries, especially the US, have done a lot of empirical studies in the area of HR practices. In India, on the other hand, no attempt has been made to systematically evaluate the extent of HRD function or its components or practices, its expected impact on the organization, and its internal working and support provided to it by the management (Pareek, 1997)

III Objectives of the research paper:

- To study how difficult the motivation has become most difficult task in organization
- To find the causes of low level of motivation among employees
- To know the positive measures that can improve the workers participation at work level.
- To find the negative measures that can enhance the motivation of your employees

IV Research Methodology:

1	Universe	Pune city
2	Research Method	Survey Method
3	Sampling Technique	Simple random Sampling
4	Research Tool	Questionnaire
5	Sample Unit	Branch managers and Level III employees
6	Sample Size	45
7	Research design	Descriptive research design

V Analysis and Interpretation:

Which methods of motivation you feel is appropriate at branch level?

Table No. 1.1

Methods of Motivation	Branch managers
Psychological needs	6
Safety needs	4
Social needs	15
Esteem needs	12
Self-actualization needs	8

Interpretation:

Most of the managers nearly 60% feel that social needs and esteem needs satisfaction is the best one in LIC for motivating employees at branch level.

Do you feel that motivation has become most difficult task in your organization/

Table No. 1.2

Motivation difficult task	Yes	No
Branch managers	31	14

Interpretation:

Large number of managers nearly 68 % feels that motivation has become a difficult task in organization. In other works branch managers to some extent feel that to make them work willingly is a difficult task for them.

At branch level staff being limited motivation becomes a tough task. Also managers of LIC and other private Companies cannot use unconventional methods of motivation. Various procedural and organizational reasons are there for low level of motivation. Hence the level of motivation at employees level is low.

What in your opinion are the causes of low level of motivation of your employees

Chart No. 1.1

Do you think that certain positive measures can improve the workers participation at work level.

TableNo.1.3

Do you think that certain positive measures can improve the workers participation at work level.	Branch manager
Performance oriented incentives	10
Simplified work procedure	6
Reduction of Procedural length	4
Encouragement to participate in decision making	3

Recognition of positive work	4
Motivation	4
Accepting good suggestion	6
Encourage to improve work at personal level	8

Interpretation : From the above performance oriented incentives and encourage to improve work at personal level are the main reasons to improve workers participation at work level nearly 40% of the branch managers mentioned these reasons.

Do you think certain Negative measures can enhance the motivation of your employees?

Table No. 1.4

	Branch managers
Negative measures to improve workers participation	
Transfer, Change of Work	7
Punishment for poor performance	6
Minimum bench mark standard	9
Minimum chances of advancements	3
Restrictive participative activities	11
Reduction in power to take Independent decisions	9

VI Conclusion:

As to various HR practices adopted by the corporation to enhance the growth of manpower planning. The true asset of any organization is its dynamic strength. The dynamism is reflected by the question of manpower planning nurtures and therefore the question of manpower planning is what the organization is. As rightly said by an expert there is no asset like human resource and therefore the development of human resource is what really worth. Human asset are

the true asset as they are enriched by experience, the ability to improve with knowledge, skill development and improve performance which are truly to great extend depend on how it frames its human resource policy.

In a present study the researcher makes an attempt to analyze how the human resource practices are developed and how practices are adopted, modified and altered by course of time. Considering the nature of study the researcher has set of selected questions collected from employees and branch managers of life Insurance corporation.

VII Suggestion:

- Need and assistance of professional trainee should be taken while formulation of various Motivation development programmes.
- The motivation evaluation mechanism is established to make an assessment of effectivity and utility of various employee within the organization.
- A suitable incentive policy should be brought to increase motivation of employees.
- Efficient and committed employees given merit based incentives to their contribution to organization development.

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